

THE IMPACT OF ACTIVITIES ON TEACHING ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

There are a number of activities and effective designed materials have been developed in order to aid pupils to gain qualified education. The role of English language books in school program is regarded as an essential element in preparing graduates for being ready to continue further education with adequate knowledge and go to the higher educational establishments. In this article we will look through the process of teaching pupils to open the door toward success, by the help of the English books and its activities centered on expanding the knowledge of pupils with varies important skills.

The English books of primary and secondary schools have undergone changes. In 2022-2023 the famous book "Fly High" has been replaced to "Guess What" from 1st to 6th grade and "Prepare" from 7th to 11th grade, these customized editions include original sources owned and licensed by the Cambridge University Press and programs which are more comfortable and instructive both in grammar and lexis. The Book "Guess What" has 2 books but the same contents, one for explaining and introducing the topics with colorful pictures, listening and speaking activities whereas the second pair of the book mostly centered on grammar, reading and writing assignments to consolidate the learned topic. In the content of the books Guess What 6 the first unit is devoted on learning Seasons and Weather, which might be boring for some pupils just

reading the words with translations from the boards which are written by teachers. Nevertheless, now by the help of the books Guess What the pupils are showing more enthusiasm and can imagine the weather-related words by looking to the pictures, listening CD tracks and at the same time complete the matching tasks. By practicing these types of activities, the pupils subconsciously improve listening skill and pronunciation which might provide them with the opportunity to understand the native speaker in the further life without any hardships even though they speak in fast speed.

Moreover, "think" and "My world" activities are more likely to evoke the pupils' interest and ability for interaction with classmates by asking and answering to the questions or give a chance to state their opinions in discussions freely. The main reason for

including these tasks is to improve speaking skill of the pupils from the early age, due to the fact that nowadays most people even students whom are studying in the faculties of English are suffering from being unable to speak, because of having fear to make mistakes and being laughed at by surrounded peers or shyness.

Therefore, teachers play an important role in encouraging pupils to learn the topics with great interest and creating warm atmosphere among them by being prepared to every lesson and make sure that each pupil is gaining knowledge not only come and think about going home, conversely with the feeling of proudness for fulfilling hopes of their parents by achieving and counting that day's results.

In the second pair of the book Guess What 6 there are mostly given exercises in order to review the learned new words and their usage in different kind of contexts. For instance, in exercise 2 in the page of 4 there are given 3 words which were learned in the first book and pupils should circle the one that does not belong to the others in meaning "**Summer, storm and fall**" here the words "**Summer and fall**" have the same meaning while the word "**Storm**" has no connection.

Besides, telling the translation of the words is regarded as a simple way of learning, that ensures short term memorization and there is no doubt that pupils may memorize the word even without realizing its meaning. For example, the word "grace" which means "smoothness and elegance of movement" in Russian translated as "грация" not all of the pupils of the 6th grade can comprehend its meaning even if they learned it by heart, therefore learning the words by looking up its definitions first is the better way of memorizing and while

utilizing the pupil will be sure that he/she picked up the proper word for that context. In the books of Guess What 6 at the page of 4 there is given an exercise with definitions and pupils should write the word for that definition by understanding its meaning, example "This is the coldest season – Winter" in this way they can practice and make this process of learning as a beneficial habit.

Moreover, pupils should not limit themselves working, only by completing the tasks which are given by the teacher, however they should attempt to gain more knowledge and improve speaking skill by reviewing the learnt topic autonomously. For instance, on the first pair of the Guess What 6 there are given "Time to talk" activities that might improve the speaking skill of the pupils by giving topic related questions. As nowadays, speaking in a foreign language seems very challenging for the people of early age, these activities will aid pupils to speak without having any hardships.

Nevertheless, in the process of practicing speaking, pupils are highly likely to make mistake both in grammar and lexis, in this kind of situations they really need support by their teachers, everyone makes mistakes even while using their L1, in second language learning to make mistakes is a natural phenomenon. Correcting mistakes is regarded as an important element in the process of learning\teaching, therefore, teachers need to make informed decisions about what, when and how to correct their pupils to improve their speaking for fluency skills and at the same time not to discourage them from the speaking at all. Pupils are very emotional and accept every word said by teacher close to heart, if the teacher says

immediately the mistake of the pupils in order to correct them by stopping her\him, they will lose interest, instead they will have fear to speak, and think only in their mind.

Therefore, while correcting the pupils' mistakes the teacher have to be very careful, without interrupting the speaking flow let pupils finish up their mind. Teacher first should monitor during speaking process and collect the errors (grammar, lexical and pronunciation) by noting them in a notebook. Then when pupil finishes speaking write on the board the mistakes, and correct them with the whole class, in this way the pupil will not feel stressed about being corrected, but analyze the speech by look through the mistakes she\he made while speaking. That is why, it is important to underline that the so-called "joy of teaching" and "joy of learning" combined are the key principles in creating positive educational environment. (UNICEF, 2006, p. 23). [2] Unfortunately, there is neither machine nor medicine that can improve speaking simply in a few days, just only practice can be a real key to success and practice always makes perfect. Buhrow and Garcia recognize, that meaningful practice results in meaningful communication, because for kids, "learning is all about exploring their passions and interests" [1].

In addition, in Guess What 6 the attention centered not only on speaking activities but also reading, writing and listening tasks are involved. On the page of 14 there is a unit about "Camping" with colorful pictures and interesting exercises to learn new vocabulary by matching the pictures in numbers with the words which are given in

the box with letters, for example, the 1st picture shows a backpack and in the box there is a letter "F" with the word backpack, this activity encourage pupils learn new topic related vocabulary more efficiently and by understanding the word exactly.

Furthermore, in the second pair of the book on page number 16, there is a reading activity in the story form that should be completed with the words given in parentheses and which is provided with a picture in the opposite side of the text helping pupils to imagine the story. The words which are given in parentheses should be completed in the right form grammatically. For instance, "Carol is a smart girl, but she always forgets things. One day, she went hiking in the jungle. It ...(start) to rain" in the given example the verb in brackets should be written in the right form present, past or future. Learning grammar can be challenging for 6th grade pupils while it deals with memorizing structure and formulas, however, when it is in the form of exercise, pupils comprehend its functions and might easily utilize them in life situations. By the reading task mentioned above pupils will practice not only grammar and reading skill but also, they will expand lexical resources while working with texts.

However, in order to make pupils work with texts properly, teachers should be strict and demand to write unknown words first, to understand the text and if the pupils are not aware of the meaning of the words in texts, it is impossible to write the verbs in the correct form without understanding the context.

References:

1. Buhrow, B., & Garcia, A. U. (2006). *Ladybugs, Tornadoes, and Swirling Galaxies: English Language Learners Discover Their World Through Inquiry*. Portsmouth, NH: Stenhouse Publishers.
2. UNICEF (2006). *Child Friendly Schools Manual*. Retrieved from [https://www.unicef.org/publications/files/Child Friendly Schools Manual EN 040809.pdf](https://www.unicef.org/publications/files/Child_Friendly_Schools_Manual_EN_040809.pdf)